

Synthesis of Some 3-Substituted-*s*-Triazolo(5, 4-*b*) Naphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole*

(Miss.) A. P. KULKARNI, S. T. JANNAWAR and D. S. DESHPANDE

Chemistry Department, Science College, Nanded-431 602

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2-Hydrazinonaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole is prepared from 2-aminonaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole in good yields. This was condensed with various aryl aldehydes. The hydrazones thus obtained could be cyclised to respective *s*-triazolo(5, 4-*b*)naphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazoles. Some of the hydrazones are found to be plant growth promoter.

LARGE amount of work has been carried out on *s*-triazoles. Very little information is available on tricyclic and tetracyclic triazoles. This gap may perhaps be due to the non-availability of efficient method for preparing their starting material. Bayer¹ was the first to report 2-hydrazinonaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(IV). It was prepared by heating 2-hydroxy, 2-chloro or 2-sulphonic acid derivatives with hydrazine hydrate. Hunter and Jones² prepared 2-halonnaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole from β -naphthylisothiocyanate. In both the cases the yields are not satisfactory. J. V. Singh³ obtained 2-chloronaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(III) from 2-mercaptanaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(II) by simple treatment of sulphuryl chloride on mercapto compound. This on subsequent treatment with hydrazine hydrate yielded 2-hydrazinonaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(IV).

In the present investigation, we have attempted the preparation of 2-hydrazinonaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(IV) from 2-mercaptanaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(II) by subjecting it to hydrazine hydrate treatment. We could directly get 2-hydrazinonaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(IV) in comparable yields. As an alternative method 2-aminonaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(V) which was obtained from naphthylisothiocyanate, was heated with hydrazine hydrate with suitable solvent. We got 2-hydrazinonaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole in very good yields. 2-Mercaptanaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(II) was converted into 2-chloronaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(III) by $\text{Cl}_2/\text{CHCl}_3$ reaction^{4,5}, and the chloro-compound was treated with hydrazine hydrate which ultimately gave hydrazinonaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(IV). The melting point of 2-hydrazinonaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole was found to be identical to the compound prepared by Mr. Singh.

In the hope of obtaining some physiologically active compounds, hydrazinonaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(IV) was condensed with various aldehydes. The hydrazones(VI) thus obtained could be cyclised by the use of nitrobenzene to the respective substituted *s*-triazolo(5, 4-*b*)naphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazoles(VII).

These hydrazones when tested against some of the organisms did not show much significant physiological activity. Instead they were found to be plant growth promoter particularly towards *Cicer arietinum*. Amongst the compounds tested salicyl and pyridyl hydrazones were found to be superior to the control and well comparable with standard.

Experimental

2-Aminonaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(V): 2-Amino-1-thiocyanatonaphthalene⁶(I) (20 g) was refluxed with ethanolic HCl (60 ml) on a hot water bath for about 10-15 minutes. The mixture cooled, poured in cold water. The precipitate obtained was filtered. It was then dried and crystallized from benzene M. P. 265°; Yield : (18.2 g).

2-Hydrazinonaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(IV): (a) Hydrazine hydrate (80% ; 6 ml) was taken in a flask, cooled to 5° and concentrated HCl (6 ml) added to it with stirring. Then ethylene glycol (24 ml) added to it. The flask was kept at room temperature for few minutes. 2-Aminonaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(V) (6 g) was added in portions to the above solution. This was refluxed for 2 hr. over an oil-bath, cooled, filtered, washed with water. Recrystallization by benzene. M. P. 220°; Yield : (4.6 g).

(b) 2-Mercaptanaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(II) (2 g) was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (80% ; 10 ml) in an oil-bath for two hours. Then it was allowed to cool. 2-Hydrazinonaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(IV) was obtained. It was filtered, washed with aqueous alkali, water and then aqueous ethanol. M. P. 218° - 220°; Yield : (0.65 g).

(c) 2-Mercaptanaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(II) (2 g) was suspended in CHCl_3 /water (2 : 1) ratio. Cooled to 5° and chlorine gas was passed in it for one hour. 2-Chloronaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(III) was isolated from chloroform layer. This 2-chloronaphtho(2, 1-*d*)-

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TABLE I—NAPHTHOTHIAZOLYL ARYL HYDRAZONES

No.	R	M.P. °C	Yields %	Molecular formula	Recrystallization solvent	Element analysis found		
						C%	H%	N%
1.	Anisyl	269	58	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{19}\text{ON}_2\text{S}$	DMF	68.3	4.1	12.0
2.	5-Chloro-2-salicyl	283	70	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{OClS}$	"	60.5	3.1	11.4
3.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	259	74	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{OS}$	"	67.2	3.8	13.0
4.	2-Thienyl	270	66	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$	"	59.7	3.2	13.3
5.	4-Pyridyl	276	64	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{S}$	"	67.0	3.7	18.1
6.	Phenyl	264	70	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{S}$	"	71.1	4.0	13.5
7.	Salicyl	250	66	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{OS}$	"	67.5	4.0	13.0

TABLE 2—3-SUBSTITUTED-*s*-TRIAZOLO(5, 4-*b*)NAPHTHO(2, 1-*d*)THIAZOLES

No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Recrystallization solvent	Element analysis found		
						C%	H%	N%
1.	Anisyl	331	40	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ ON ₃ S	Ethanol	68.0	3.8	12.2
2.	5-Chloro-2-salicyl	258	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₃ OClS	"	60.2	2.6	11.5
3.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	above 340	50	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ OS	"	67.4	3.0	12.0
4.	2-Thienyl	330	40	C ₁₈ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂	"	59.0	2.9	12.8
5.	4-Pyridyl	141	42	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	"	67.0	3.0	18.2
6.	Phenyl	323	48	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ S	"	70.2	3.4	13.7
7.	Salicyl	300	48	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ OS	"	67.7	3.4	13.0

thiazole(III) was directly treated with hydrazine hydrate to obtain 2-hydrazinonaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(IV). M. P. 219°; Yield: (0.70 g).

Naphthothiazolyl hydrazones: Equimolar proportions of 2-hydrazinonaphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazole(IV) and the aldehyde, in ethanol refluxed on hot water-bath for 30 minutes. It was cooled, filtered and dried. Recrystallized from DMF. The yields, m.p.'s and analytical data, etc., are included in Table 1.

3-Substituted-*s*-triazolo(5, 4-*b*)naphtho(2, 1-*d*)thiazoles: These compounds are obtained by oxidative cyclization of the hydrazones(IV) using nitrobenzene.

Results

After disinfection with a solution of sodium hypochlorite (2% available chlorine) for 10 min., the seeds of *Cicer arietinum* were soaked for 4 hours in the 5 ppm solution of the hydrazone. Then seeds were sown on blotter in a petridish. The blotters were sterilized at 15 psi for 20 min. before use. The blotters were moistened with 5 ppm solution of the

compounds. Along with these compounds gibberellic acid was used as standard and sterile water was kept as control.

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